

22RPT03 MultiFixRad

D2: Report detailing the progress made by the less experienced NMIs/DIs during the project in developing capability in the temperatures scale realisation within ITS-90 and the MeP-K at higher temperatures

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Due date of the deliverable:
31 May 2026

Actual submission date of the deliverable:
04 June 2026

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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Emerging laboratories progress report in the area of radiation thermometry

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1 Introduction

This report presents the progress achieved by the less experienced National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs) participating in the project aimed at strengthening capabilities in temperature scale realisation according to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) and the Mise en Pratique for the definition of the kelvin (MeP-K) at higher temperatures. The project has focused on enhancing technical competence, improving measurement infrastructure, and supporting the development of reliable and traceable temperature measurement practices among the participating institutes.

Throughout the project, the NMIs/DIs have engaged in a range of technical activities, including training, knowledge transfer, practical implementation of fixed-point realisations, uncertainty evaluation, and participation in comparison measurements. These activities have contributed to a better understanding of high-temperature thermometry techniques and the practical application of ITS-90 and MeP-K recommendations. In addition, the collaboration between experienced and developing institutes has fostered the exchange of expertise and promoted harmonisation of measurement procedures across the participating laboratories.

The report summarises the main achievements, challenges encountered, and the overall impact of the project on the participating institutes' metrological capabilities. It also highlights the progress made towards establishing sustainable competence in high-temperature scale realisation and supporting future regional and international cooperation in thermometry.

2 Status before the project

This section summarises the status of each individual NMI/DI before the start of the MultiFixRad project in terms of radiation thermometry and their developments on the realisation of the scale and MeP-K.

2.1 Czech Institute of metrology (CMI)

CMI had already established calibration and measurement services covering the temperature range from approximately -30 °C up to 1800 °C . For temperatures below 1000 °C , traceability to the ITS-90 was realised using standard platinum resistance thermometers (SPRTs) and thermocouples. In the higher temperature range above 1000 °C , traceability was established through radiation thermometry means by extrapolation from the copper fixed point using a linear pyrometer LP5 operating at a wavelength of 650 nm .

The laboratory possessed several important elements of infrastructure required for high-temperature thermometry. The copper fixed point was realised in a sodium heat-pipe furnace, providing the basis for radiometric traceability at elevated temperatures. Additional available equipment included the LP5 linear pyrometer, a high-temperature furnace with both horizontal and vertical arrangements, although this system was not operational at the start of the project. As an alternative for the filling of fixed-point cells an inductive furnace with a maximum operational temperature of 1500 °C was used. CMI laboratory also had available stocks of cobalt, palladium, and carbon materials (in their raw form) intended for the preparation of high-temperature fixed points. Despite the existing capabilities, several limitations were identified in relation to the practical realisation of ITS-90 and MeP-K at higher temperatures. In particular, the laboratory lacked experience in the fabrication and implementation of high-temperature fixed points, optimisation of furnace operation, and advanced uncertainty evaluation for radiometric thermometry. The CMI project activities therefore aimed not only to improve the technical infrastructure, but also to develop the practical expertise and confidence necessary for sustainable operation and future dissemination of high-temperature traceability.

2.2 Danish Fundamental Metrology (DFM)

At the beginning of the project, DFM had only limited capabilities in the field of radiation thermometry and high-temperature scale realisation. While the laboratory-maintained experience in conventional temperature

measurements and calibration activities, its infrastructure and expertise related to radiometric thermometry and high-temperature fixed points were still at an early stage of development.

The laboratory possessed aluminium (660.323 °C), silver (961.78 °C) and copper (1084.62 °C) fixed-point cells, which provided a basic reference for the realisation of the ITS-90 at elevated temperatures. However, the available fixed points did not allow for a broader implementation of high-temperature interpolation procedures or advanced radiometric applications required for extending the scale to higher temperatures in accordance with the MeP-K recommendations. At the start of the project, DFM also had no practical capability or prior experience in the design, construction, and characterisation of radiation thermometers or pyrometers. Knowledge related to optical alignment, detector selection, spectral filtering, signal processing, and uncertainty evaluation for radiation thermometry was limited. As a result, the laboratory relied mainly on existing commercial instrumentation and lacked the competence required for independent development and optimisation of radiometric measurement systems.

2.3 Justervesenet (JV)

At the beginning of the project, JV possessed well-established capabilities for the realisation and dissemination of the ITS-90 temperature scale in the low- and medium-temperature ranges. The laboratory was able to realise the temperature scale from the triple point of argon (−189.3442 °C) up to the freezing point of copper (1084.62 °C). Standard platinum resistance thermometers (SPRTs) were used for temperatures below 660 °C, while thermocouples provided traceability at higher temperatures up to the copper point. For radiation thermometry applications, the laboratory operated several variable-temperature blackbody sources covering the range from 5 °C to 1600 °C. These blackbodies were used as standards for the calibration of pyrometers and infrared calibrators, with traceability established through contact thermometry methods. JV also utilised a Diadem DS09 radiation thermometer together with two Heitronics radiation thermometers (TRT II and TRT IV) as transfer standards for calibration activities involving blackbodies and infrared calibration systems.

Despite these existing capabilities, the laboratory had no infrastructure or practical experience for the direct realisation of the temperature scale using radiation thermometry methods at high temperatures. In particular, JV did not possess the equipment required for implementing the ITS-90 above the copper point through radiometric techniques, nor any capability related to the multiple fixed-point approach promoted within the MeP-K framework. The laboratory therefore relied entirely on contact thermometry traceability and lacked independent radiometric scale realisation capability. Several important gaps in equipment and infrastructure were identified at the start of the project. The laboratory did not have a dedicated furnace for melting and preparing fixed-point ingots, nor a furnace suitable for the practical realisation of high-temperature fixed points. In addition, JV lacked a reference-grade radiation thermometer suitable for accurate scale realisation and interpolation work. No dedicated furnace for scale transfer or dissemination at high temperatures was available either, limiting the laboratory's ability to provide advanced calibration services in radiation thermometry. The project therefore represented an important opportunity for JV to establish foundational capabilities in high-temperature radiometric thermometry. Through the acquisition of new equipment, development of practical expertise, and collaboration with experienced partners, the laboratory aimed to extend its competence beyond conventional contact thermometry and develop the ability to realise, maintain, and disseminate the temperature scale using high-temperature fixed points and radiation thermometry techniques.

2.4 Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE)

At the beginning of the project, RISE already possessed extensive capabilities in temperature metrology and operated calibration and measurement services covering a wide temperature range, from the triple point of argon (−189.3442 °C) up to 2600 °C. The laboratory maintained a well-established implementation of the ITS-90 temperature scale, using SPRTs and thermocouples for temperatures up to the silver point (961.78 °C). For higher temperatures, the scale was realised using a linear pyrometer LP5 operating above the silver point.

In the high-temperature region, the practical realisation of the ITS-90 was based primarily on conventional fixed points up to the freezing point of copper (1084.62 °C). To support validation of the radiometric scale realisation at elevated temperatures, RISE had previously acquired a Pt–C eutectic fixed-point cell with a temperature of approximately 1738 °C. In addition, a Co–C fixed-point cell originally intended for thermocouple

calibration purposes was also available. These fixed points provided an initial basis for exploring high-temperature fixed-point techniques and for validating radiation thermometry measurements beyond the copper point. RISE also operated a comprehensive range of variable-temperature blackbody sources covering temperatures from $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $2200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. These blackbodies served as standards for the calibration of pyrometers and infrared calibrators, with traceability established through contact thermometry methods at lower temperatures and via the LP5 pyrometer at elevated temperatures. Several radiation thermometers were available as transfer standards, including two Cyclops/Land instruments (C33 and C52), one Mikron M190 pyrometer, and two Heitronics radiation thermometers (TRT II and TRT IV), supporting both internal measurement activities and customer calibration services. RISE also possessed significant technical infrastructure related to fixed-point thermometry. The laboratory operated a furnace capable of realising fixed-point cells up to approximately $1800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and another furnace intended for the manufacturing of fixed-point cells which can reach temperatures of $1600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In terms of measurement devices, a reference-grade LP5 pyrometer was available for radiometric scale realisation and dissemination.

Despite the advanced status of the laboratory compared with several project partners, important limitations still existed in relation to the practical implementation of high-temperature fixed-point techniques at the highest temperatures. In particular, RISE lacked dedicated furnace systems suitable for manufacturing fixed-point cells above $1600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and for realising high-temperature fixed points above approximately $1800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. These limitations restricted the laboratory's ability to fully implement and expand the multiple fixed-point approach promoted within the MeP-K framework and to realise the temperature scale with lower uncertainties at the highest temperatures.

2.5 Slovak Institute of Metrology (SMU)

At the beginning of the project, SMU had capabilities in temperature metrology and operated calibration and measurement services covering a wide temperature range, from the triple point of Hg ($-38.8344\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) up to $1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The laboratory maintained a well-established implementation of the ITS-90 temperature scale, using SPRTs and thermocouples for temperatures up to the Cu point ($1084.62\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). For higher temperatures, the scale was realised using a linear pyrometer.

In terms of radiation thermometry SMU had limited capabilities and practical implementation of the ITS-90 above the gold point. The laboratory infrastructure was primarily based on a commercial Au fixed-point cell ($1064.18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), which served as the main reference for high-temperature measurements. Using this fixed point, SMU was able to establish traceability through extrapolation methods in accordance with the ITS-90. However, the laboratory did not yet possess the capability for direct realisation of multiple high-temperature fixed points or for interpolation between fixed points using advanced radiometric techniques. The laboratory operated several commercial blackbody cavities that were used for calibration and dissemination purposes in radiation thermometry. These blackbody sources provided the basis for practical non-contact temperature measurements and supported calibration activities involving radiation thermometers and pyrometers. Traceability at elevated temperatures was mainly dependent on extrapolation from the gold fixed point and on the use of commercially available instrumentation.

At the start of the project, SMU utilised a combination of commercial pyrometers together with an in-house-built radiation thermometer for experimental activities. While these instruments provided a foundation for radiation thermometry measurements, the laboratory had only limited experience with the characterisation, optimisation, and uncertainty evaluation of pyrometric systems intended for high-accuracy scale realisation. In particular, practical expertise related to spectral responsivity, size-of-source effect, linearity evaluation, and interpolation between high-temperature fixed points was still under development.

The lack of in-house capability for manufacturing and filling high-temperature fixed-point cells was limiting the capabilities of SMU in the field of radiation thermometry. The laboratory did not yet possess established procedures for preparing pure-metal or carbon–metal eutectic fixed points incorporating blackbody cavities, which are essential elements of the multiple fixed-point approach promoted by the MeP-K framework. As a result, SMU relied mainly on commercially available standards and had limited flexibility for developing customised fixed-point solutions for advanced radiometric thermometry applications.

2.6 University of Ljubljana (UL)

At the beginning of the project, UL had capabilities in temperature metrology and operated calibration and measurement services covering a wide temperature range, from the triple point of Hg (-38.8344 °C) up to 1100 °C . The laboratory maintained a well-established implementation of the ITS-90 temperature scale, using SPRTs and thermocouples for temperatures up to the Ag point (961.78 °C).

Before the start of the project, UL had only very limited infrastructure and practical capability related to high-temperature non-contact thermometry and the implementation of eutectic fixed-point techniques. In particular, the laboratory did not possess facilities for the manufacturing and filling of carbon–metal eutectic fixed-point cells intended for radiation thermometry applications. As a result, UL had no established capability for producing its own high-temperature fixed points or for independently supporting the multiple fixed-point approach within the framework of the MeP-K.

From the hardware perspective, the laboratory lacked dedicated furnace systems required for the preparation and filling of eutectic fixed-point cells. No suitable high-temperature furnace for melting and processing eutectic materials was available, which significantly limited experimental work related to fixed-point fabrication. In addition, the laboratory did not possess a dedicated furnace for the practical realisation and operation of eutectic fixed points during radiometric measurements and scale dissemination activities. These limitations meant that UL had only restricted possibilities for participating in advanced high-temperature radiation thermometry activities prior to the project. Practical experience with the handling of eutectic materials, construction of blackbody fixed-point cells, optimisation of thermal conditions during filling, and operation of high-temperature fixed points was also limited.

3 Status at the end of project

This section summarises the status of each individual NMI/DI at the end of the MultiFixRad project in terms of radiation thermometry and their developments on the realisation of the scale and MeP-K.

3.1 Czech Institute of metrology (CMI)

During the course of the project, significant progress was achieved in the development of CMI's high-temperature radiation thermometry capabilities and laboratory infrastructure. One of the key milestones was the restoration and gradual recommissioning of the Thermogauge high-temperature furnace. In March 2024, a new cooling chiller was installed to support safe furnace operation. Initial testing of the furnace in the horizontal configuration revealed technical issues related to the cooling system, which required the replacement of cooling medium tubes and additional safety improvements. By May 2026, the Thermogauge furnace was fully operational again, equipped with new cooling tubes and a new display unit, with final testing and optimisation still in progress. The laboratory also strengthened its capability in the preparation and implementation of high-temperature fixed points (HTFPs). Crucible components became available in 2024, and despite temporary limitations in personnel capacity, which improved after the partial return of one employee in October 2024, work on fixed-point fabrication continued steadily. Following the delivery of rhenium material in December 2024, CMI successfully implemented both the step-by-step and piston filling methods for fixed-point cell fabrication. By the end of the project, a total of four HTFP cells had been prepared and filled. Specifically, one Co–C cell, one Pd–C cell, and two Re–C cells. Subsequent work also included the filling of additional Co–C cells using the vertical inductive furnace, with plans to construct cells based on the MultiFixRad design, including dedicated fixed points for thermocouple applications. Substantial improvements were also achieved in practical radiometric thermometry. The laboratory successfully realised the Co–C (1324.24 °C) fixed point and extended the temperature scale up to this temperature. Furthermore, the relative spectral characterisation of the LP5 linear pyrometer was repeated, and corrections related to the size-of-source effect (SSE) were implemented into the calculation of reference temperatures, improving the accuracy and reliability of high-temperature measurements. At the conclusion of the project, CMI possessed the technical tools and expertise necessary to realise the temperature scale up to approximately 2500 °C , either

by interpolation between fixed points or by extrapolation from available fixed points. Equally important, the laboratory significantly deepened its practical understanding of its own equipment and measurement procedures. This enhanced competence is expected to lead to further improvements in calibration and measurement services provided to customers in the near future.

3.2 Danish Fundamental Metrology (DFM)

During the project, DFM, in close collaboration with its partner DTU (Technical University of Denmark), achieved substantial progress in the development of radiation thermometry and high-temperature scale realisation capabilities within the framework of the MultiFixRad project. Starting from a laboratory with only limited experience in radiometric thermometry, DFM successfully established both the technical infrastructure and practical expertise required for advanced implementation of the ITS-90 at high temperatures. A major achievement was the design, construction, and operation of two dedicated high-temperature furnaces equipped with MoSi₂ heating elements. A vertical furnace was successfully developed and operated at temperatures as high as 1700 °C, enabling the preparation and realisation of high-temperature fixed points. In parallel, a horizontal furnace was constructed specifically for the practical realisation of the ITS-90 and for interpolation between fixed points up to the Pd–C (1492 °C) temperature. These developments significantly expanded the laboratory's experimental capabilities for high-temperature radiometric measurements.

DFM also extended its portfolio of fixed-point cells through the successful fabrication and implementation of Co–C and Pd–C high-temperature fixed points in collaboration with DTU. These new fixed points complemented the laboratory's existing silver, copper, and aluminium fixed points and enabled improved interpolation and traceability across a much wider temperature range. During the project, DFM successfully realised the Co–C and Pd–C fixed points at approximately 1321.3 °C and 1492.1 °C with an expanded uncertainty of ±0.6 °C ($k = 2$), respectively. Another important milestone was the successful development of a homebuilt camera-based interpolating pyrometer. The pyrometer was constructed, characterised, and experimentally verified within the project. The laboratory carried out measurements of the size-of-source effect (SSE) and linearity of the instrument, providing important information for uncertainty evaluation and performance optimisation. Participation in the Scandinavian intercomparison campaign organised by RISE in February 2026 further validated the performance of the pyrometer in the temperature range from 961 °C to 1700 °C through comparison with measurements performed by JV and RISE using the RISE blackbody facility.

The work remains ongoing, particularly in relation to further reducing uncertainties in the ITS-90 realisation between 961 °C and 1492 °C and improving interpolation procedures between fixed points. DFM is also continuing its involvement in international activities, including participation in the Euramet.T-K10 interlaboratory comparison.

3.3 Justervesenet (JV)

JV has significantly improved the capacity in three main ways: in construction and operation of fixed points, in construction and operation of radiation thermometers, and in developing software for data analysis relevant in fixed point-based scale implementations. But these high-level improvements are supported by a number of smaller modifications and extension of the laboratory facilities.

Fixed points: JV has created a setup for ingot melting that works up to the Cu point. It incorporates a system to ensure inert gas atmosphere during the process, with access to push the piston down at the right moment during the melt. For higher temperatures JV and RISE have established a close collaboration and all the cells with melting temperatures above the Cu point have been constructed there. In essence the setup at RISE comprises a similar design, but uses furnaces with a much higher maximum temperature. In total, JV has constructed 1 Al cell, 1 Ag cell, 1 Cu cell (on JV premises), 1 Fe–C cell, 1 Co–C cell, 1 Pd–C cell and two Pt–C cells (at RISE). All cells have been tested in the setup at JV except Al and Pt–C, but work is in progress to modify a furnace to accommodate the Pt–C cell. The Al cell requires a new radiation thermometer setup first (see below).

In order to induce the plateaus a simple one-zone tube furnace is typically used, with an upper operational temperature of 1600 °C. This means that all cells except the Pt–C cell (1738.28 °C) can be realised in the

furnace. During the project, almost all plateau realisations have been carried out in a work tube with 25 mm inner diameter, just large enough to fit a cell. Some of the most recent experiments were carried out with a larger work tube (50 mm) and the cell fitted inside a graphite holder. The idea is to try to improve the gradients slightly in the location of the cell, enable a larger objective in the radiation thermometer without risking obscuration from the work tube, and to protect the cell better. The furnace has an inert gas system with gas injection from both sides. The Ag, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C and Pd-C cells have been realised multiple times, with Pd-C the cell that has been tested most.

JV has constructed a radiation thermometer in 4 iterations. Each of them has added a new component or feature to improve performance. The introduction of a beam chopper, internal compartments to block stray light, heater to control the temperature of the filter and the Lyot stop, and a camera as a view finder have been important modifications from the initial device. An SSE setup has been constructed with an integrating sphere and an obscuration target to measure the indirect SSE curve. There are some limitations to the setup at present. The maximum aperture is only $\text{\O}20$ mm, and the light power is smaller than ideal. A dedicated instrument rack has been equipped to hold all the instrumentation needed to read the signal, to control the temperature of the filter, and to operate the fan that acts as a beam chopper. The basic software to communicate with the devices, read raw traces of the chopped beam signal, and processing to produce a simple voltage as output has been implemented in Matlab, but not yet as a GUI standalone program. This is work to be completed. However, some simple setups of the instruments have been implemented to enable operation in two different modes, where the instrument setup and signal processing is slightly different: a mode for normal operation as a thermometer, and a mode to run SSE measurements. The software also converts a signal to temperature, based on a calibration at fixed points.

JV has developed software to handle two stages of the data processing. The first is a suite of methods to extract the plateau features. They are currently partly interactive but runs mostly independent of user input. The methods extract the point of inflection, assigns an uncertainty to the value based on the noise and plateau shape, identification of the first and last melt, identification of the liquidus point from the intersection method, and finally the melting range. Analysis of the freeze is not yet implemented and is performed manually.

From the fixed point data a suite of methods allow curve fitting or constant computation for the 1-point, 2-point, 3-point and >3-point schemes. The methods also computes an uncertainty in use based on a combined uncertainty at the calibration points. The uncertainty budget as such is not implemented in the software, but in separate Excel sheets instead. The code will be published to Github after final checks and verification.

3.4 Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE)

RISE has significantly improved its measurement capabilities in several ways as a result of the MultiFixRad project. This was achieved in construction and operation of fixed points, in a new furnace for their manufacturing and realization at higher temperature ranges of the ITS-90, in the characterisation of the LP 5 reference pyrometer, and in developing software for data analysis relevant in fixed point-based scale implementations. These high-level improvements are supported by several smaller modifications and extension of the laboratory facilities. The project has also deepened the collaboration between RISE and several other European NMIs, especially DFM and JV.

In the area of fixed points RISE has extended the setup for manufacturing fixed-point cells with a new furnace that now extends the temperature range up to about 3000 °C, enabling the manufacture of a Re-C (2474.69 °C) fixed-points. The significant experience gained in the project, as well as modifications and improvements made to new and existing equipment has streamlined the process of manufacturing fixed-point cells. Some of these improvements include new dust hood in the lab for filling cells, Ar gas setup that allows an easy supply of inert shielding gas to several furnaces, a new furnace for higher temperatures as well as several graphite parts for use in the furnaces.

In total, RISE has constructed one Ag cell, two Cu cell, one Fe-C cell, one Co-C cell, one Pd-C cell and one Re-C cell. All cells have been tested in terms of their realization. The use of the fixed-point cells manufactured in this project in the existing furnace required the addition of several graphite parts that were designed and manufactured within the project. A new high temperature furnace was installed in parallel to the project and

has also been used extensively once it was up and running. The Ag, Cu, Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C and Re-C cells have been realised multiple times, with the Cu cell being the one that has been tested the most.

For higher temperatures RISE have established a close collaboration with JV and DFM. Especially JV that has not had the equipment to manufacture cells with melting temperatures above the Cu point. These have all therefore been constructed at RISE since there are furnaces with a much higher maximum temperature than those available at JV. Both JV and DFM has visited RISE for a comparison at temperatures between the silver point and 1800 °C.

The LP 5 pyrometer at RISE is used as a reference for high temperatures. During the project this pyrometer has been extensively used together with the new high temperature fixed-point cells. It has also been characterised in terms of linearity and size of source effect. A new equipment was developed for this which consisted of a temperature stabilised LED-based light source together with additional accessories for the two measurements. The pyrometer has also been re-calibrated with the use of the new high temperature fixed-points.

RISE has developed several pieces of software for handling the data processing of the melting curves from the fixed-points to extract the temperature from the plateau. The program calculates the point of inflection from the curve using the derivative of a curve fitted to the melting curve. Several other pieces of software were also developed to solve specific tasks in characterising the pyrometer as well as the furnaces used for the realisation of the fixed-points.

3.5 Slovak Institute of Metrology (SMU)

SMU developed the methodology and optimised the required hardware to fill carbon crucibles for both pure-metal and eutectic fixed-point cells using a piston-filling method. This technique enables reliable and repeatable preparation of fixed-point cells with appropriate blackbody cavity geometry for radiation thermometry applications.

Using these methods, SMU has successfully constructed and tested a series of high-temperature fixed-point cells. To date, this includes one Ag cell, one Cu cell, one Au cell, one Fe-C eutectic cell, two Co-C eutectic cells, and two Pd-C eutectic cells. The availability of these cells represents a substantial increase in the institute's capability to realise high-temperature reference points for radiation thermometry. For the realisation of these fixed points, SMU uses two dedicated furnaces designed to produce the melting and freezing plateaus of the pure-metal and eutectic cells. The furnace set-points and thermal profiles required careful adjustment and optimisation in order to achieve stable and reproducible phase transitions, which are essential for high-accuracy temperature realisation. In parallel, the optical alignment and optical components of the measurement system were optimised for each specific combination of fixed-point cell and furnace. These adjustments were performed in conjunction with the radiation thermometer used in the measurements, the Chino IR-RST65H, which has a spot size of approximately 1 mm at a distance of 800 mm. The pyrometer itself was also characterised to ensure reliable measurements, including investigations of its linearity and spectral responsivity. This characterisation supports the accurate application of radiation thermometry methods across the relevant temperature range.

As a result of these developments, SMU can now perform calibrations using blackbody fixed-point cells in the temperature range from 961.78 °C up to approximately 1492 °C. As a result of these efforts and subsequent measurements, SMU has established the capability to apply the Sakuma–Hattori Equation. This ability represent additional tool to increase the precision of already used extrapolation from a single ITS-90 fixed point for high-temperature radiation thermometry measurements. Overall, the activities carried out during the project have significantly strengthened SMU's capability in the realisation and dissemination of the high-temperature scale, representing a substantial advancement compared to the capabilities available prior to the project.

3.6 University of Ljubljana (UL)

During the course of the project, UL achieved substantial progress in establishing technical infrastructure and practical expertise for high-temperature fixed-point thermometry and non-contact temperature scale realisation. A major achievement was the successful design and construction of dedicated furnace systems

for both the fabrication and realisation of high-temperature fixed-point cells, significantly expanding the laboratory's capabilities in the field of radiation thermometry.

Within the project, UL developed a custom high-temperature furnace capable of operation up to approximately 1600 °C. The furnace was equipped with Kanthal heating elements, a specialised alumina working tube enabling operation under an argon atmosphere, and a computer-controlled DC power supply allowing stable and programmable temperature control. This represented the first dedicated infrastructure at UL specifically intended for the preparation and processing of eutectic and pure-metal fixed-point cells.

All fixed-point cells were manufactured using a custom-built vertical filling furnace operating within a sealed alumina tube under a controlled argon atmosphere. A vacuum pump system was implemented to replace air with high-purity argon gas, minimising oxidation during the filling process. High-purity materials purchased through the project included copper, carbon powder, and cobalt with purity levels of 99.9999 %, iron with 99.999 %, and palladium with 99.99 % purity. Following successful testing of the furnace systems, UL proceeded with the fabrication of several high-temperature fixed-point cells. In total, one copper fixed-point cell, one Co–C cell, one Fe–C cell, and one Pd–C fixed-point cell were successfully prepared and filled. These fixed points substantially expanded the laboratory's capability for implementing high-temperature interpolation and radiometric traceability.

For the practical realisation of the fixed points, UL also constructed a dedicated horizontal furnace system. The furnace incorporated a 25 mm diameter and 70 cm long working tube together with seven independently controlled heating zones distributed across the central section of the furnace. Temperature gradients were monitored using thirteen thermocouples positioned throughout the ceramic tube assembly, enabling detailed mapping and optimisation of furnace uniformity. The complete system was controlled using a dedicated LabView-based software environment, allowing regulation of individual zone temperatures, heating rates, and thermal gradients along the furnace axis. Experimental testing demonstrated that a near-zero thermal gradient provided the most stable conditions for fixed-point plateau realisation. High-purity argon gas (5 N) was continuously supplied through the sealed ceramic tube assembly to maintain a protective atmosphere during operation. Additional sacrificial graphite and ceramic tubes were positioned in front of the fixed-point cells to minimise convective currents and reduce the influence of residual oxygen contamination.

Considerable progress was also achieved in the practical implementation of radiation thermometry techniques. The pyrometer alignment procedure was optimised using a coordinate positioning table with two rotational axes, enabling accurate centring of the pyrometer on the blackbody cavity. During melting and freezing operations, scans of the cavity front surface were performed to enhance cavity contrast, and mathematical fitting of the resulting bell-shaped radial sigmoid curve was used to determine the precise cavity centre position.

Overall, the project enabled UL to establish complete foundational capability for the fabrication, realisation, and operation of high-temperature fixed-point cells. The laboratory significantly improved its understanding of furnace operation, atmosphere control, thermal gradient optimisation, and radiometric measurement techniques, creating a strong basis for future implementation of the ITS-90 and MeP-K at elevated temperatures.

4 Conclusion

The MultiFixRad project significantly strengthened the high-temperature radiation thermometry capabilities of all participating emerging laboratories through the development of infrastructure, fixed-point technology, pyrometry, and data analysis methods related to the ITS-90 and MeP-K frameworks. Across the consortium, major progress was achieved in the fabrication and realisation of high-temperature fixed-point (HTFP) cells, the construction and optimisation of dedicated furnaces, and the development and characterisation of radiation thermometers and pyrometers. In total 43 fixed point cells were manufactured throughout the listed laboratories and included pure metal and eutectic fixed-point cells that cover a temperature range from 660 °C up to 2475 °C.

CMI restored and upgraded its high-temperature fixed point realisations, implemented advanced LP5 pyrometer corrections, and established capabilities for scale realisation up to approximately 2500 °C through interpolation and extrapolation methods.

DFM, in collaboration with DTU, developed vertical and horizontal MoSi₂ furnaces, realised Co–C and Pd–C fixed points, and successfully constructed and validated a camera-based interpolating pyrometer.

JV significantly expanded its expertise through the construction of multiple fixed-point cells, iterative development of custom radiation thermometers, and creation of software tools for plateau analysis and scale interpolation.

RISE further enhanced its already advanced facilities by extending fixed-point manufacturing capabilities up to 3000 °C, constructing a Re–C fixed point, improving LP5 pyrometer characterisation, and strengthening international collaboration activities.

SMU established in-house capability for piston-filling both pure-metal and eutectic fixed-point cells and developed practical expertise in the application of the Sakuma–Hattori Equation for high-temperature radiation thermometry.

UL established complete foundational infrastructure for HTFP fabrication and realisation, including custom-designed filling and realisation furnaces with advanced atmosphere and thermal-gradient control systems.

Overall, the project enabled all participating institutes to substantially improve their competence in high-temperature thermometry, expand traceability capabilities, and strengthen collaboration within the European metrology community. The activities carried out during the MultiFixRad project created a strong technical basis for future implementation, dissemination, and further development of the ITS-90 and MeP-K at elevated temperatures.